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BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF GREEN TOURISM IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS BY INTERNATIONAL TOURISM COMPANIES

БІБЛІОМЕТРИЧНИЙ АНАЛІЗ ЗЕЛЕНОГО ТУРИЗМУ ПРИ ВИКОНАННІ ЦІЛЕЙ СТАЛОГО РОЗВИТКУ МІЖНАРОДНИМИ ТУРИСТИЧНИМИ КОМПАНІЯМИ

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The main goal of this study is to conduct a bibliometric analysis of green tourism in the context of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies. In the course of the conducted bibliometric analysis, the main scientific schools and scientists in the world who study green tourism were considered. When conducting a bibliometric analysis, the interaction of the main definitions, which interact to the definition of green tourism, was revealed. The main prerequisites and factors of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies have been studied. Proposals for the development of green tourism in the context of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies at the level of EU countries and Ukraine have been formulated, taking into account its post-war state.

Keywords: green tourism, companies, analysis, goals of sustainable development

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In the conditions of the accelerated development of productive forces, the movement to Industry 5.0 and the transition of business processes to their sustainable development, international tourism companies pay more and more attention to their sustainability and the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals. In turn, this increases the differentiation of tourist services and expands tourism market segments. Green tourism is one of the areas of tourism activity of companies, which is aimed at

increasing the integration of tourist services in the direction of protecting and protecting the natural environment and reducing destructive factors that affect it, primarily anthropogenic action. The direction of green tourism corresponds to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 6-8, 11-15) and is one of the directions of effective work of international tourism companies in the world market of tourist services. On the part of customers, it should also be noted the growth of customer orientation to tourist services, which include a careful attitude to environmental protection and the reduction of the cost of green tourist services in comparison with classic tourism. It should also be noted that the transition to sustainability is characterized by the transformation of company processes from economic advantages to ecological significance, this means both eco-orientation and socialization of the orientation of tourist services, depending on the level of development of the country's economy. The higher the level of economic development of the country and the level of technological development, the greater is the movement of tourist services towards ecological significance, environmental protection in the work of international tourism companies. All this makes it possible to note the importance and actualization of scientific research on green tourism in the system of implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies and the need to study the main scientific directions in the field of green tourism by adding the tools of bibliography, which is bibliometric analysis.

Formulation of the problem. Among the main issues of the research is establishing the relationship between the work of international tourism companies in the field of green tourism and the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals in the scientific works of the world's leading scientific schools.

It should be noted that the level of economic development of the countries of the world has a significant impact on the development of environmentally oriented business areas, such as green tourism. It must be stated that countries with developed economies develop more ecologically oriented projects than countries with developing and transitional economies, where the priority is the economic component of business, rather than the ecological one.

The formation of key areas of green tourism development in order to form modern trends in the field of tourism, which in turn can be useful in the development of national and international grant programs for the protection and protection of the natural environment when using the organizational mechanism of green tourism by companies that provide tourist services. Also, the main problematic aspect is the financing of environmentally oriented projects, primarily in countries with developing and transition economies. The results of scientific research on green tourism can be useful in grant support for ecologically oriented initiatives in the tourism industry, where a mechanism for grant support for green tourism can be formed at the expense of scientific institutions and universities through the applications of major scientific schools in the system of RnD projects. It is bibliometric analysis that can contribute to the analysis of modern trends and directions of green tourism in the world by evaluating the results of scientific works and scientific research works on this topic.

It should also be noted the solution to the problems of environmental education, as an element of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (STG 8). It is the level of this education that is the main motivator for the formation of environmental orientation in society and sustainability in one's life, and for tourism companies it can be an increase in the level of qualification of employees in the work process. The use of bibliometric analysis of green tourism is a factor in solving the problems of ignorance and lack of information regarding the development of alternative directions of tourist work of international tour operators, which is green tourism.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Let's examine the main scientific works related to green tourism in the work of international tourism companies in the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals. Scientists Shang, Y., Bi, C., Wei, X., Taghizadeh-Hesary, F., Rasoulinezhad, E. [1] studied the implementation of green (eco) tourism, climate change and environmental policy in the work of companies in developing countries. Scientists Sunarya E., Nur T., Rachmawati I., Suwiryo D.H., Jamaludin M. [2] considered the effects of socio-demographic factors that influence the formation of associations between innovators and green suppliers in the tourism sector. Scientific staff Tandon A., Dhir A., Madan P., Srivastava S., Nicolau J.L. [3] analyzed the receipt of green income from the implementation of the management system of male resources of tourism companies, as a factor in increasing the role of the company's staff orientation towards green tourism. Specialists Xu D., Shang Y., Yang Q., Chen H. [4] investigated the age structures of customers, with an emphasis on retirement age, who use green tourism. Scientists Van Rensburg T.M., Brennan N., Howard A. [5] investigated the benefits of renting green hydrogen vehicles for the implementation of green tourism services in Spain. Specialists Kizanlikli M.M., Margazieva N., Asanova K., Gundogdu I. [6] formed a model of ecological labeling of eco-hotels in the system of promotion of green tourist services in Kyrgyzstan. Author Dave D. [7] noted the importance of using the potential of ecotourism for sustainable development. Scientist Hasan A.A.-T. [8] explored theoretical propositions of green consumption behavior (TGCB) using the example of agro-tourism for sustainable communities and cities of the future in Bangladesh. Scientist Fox K. [9] explored green tourism by international travel companies in Hawaii as a path toward sustainable development for US travel companies. Scientists Fernández-Palacios Y., Kaushik S., Abramic A., Magalhães M., Haroun R. [10] noted the state and prospects of the blue economy sectors in the Macaronesian archipelagos as an element of the development of green tourism. Specialists Chen Y., Zhang J., Chen H. [11] analyzed the sustainable development of tourism in China, which makes it possible to focus on

As can be seen from the conducted analysis, representatives of the Great Britain, the USA, China, Australia, Spain, Portugal, Malaysia, and Indonesia are the leaders of the scientific schools that research green tourism and whose works are indexed in the Scopus database. This is primarily due to the development of their own markets for tourist services, which are focused on green tourism programs in the countries.

In order to improve the quality of the bibliometric analysis, we will also perform the same task, but with the analysis of another platform App.dimensions.ai [23] (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Bibliometric analysis of the main authors from the countries by citation, who conducted research on green tourism in the work of international tour operators based on the App.dimensions.ai platform (author research using the VOSviewer 1.19 program)

Based on the App.dimensions.ai platform [23], 518,000 publications containing scientific publications on green tourism research were processed. In the course of the conducted bibliometric analysis, it was established that the leading countries of representatives of scientific schools that study green tourism are Great Britain, USA, Malaysia, Pakistan, Turkey, Italy, Germany, India. This is also evidenced by the connections between scientists who research the topic of green tourism in the activities of international tourism companies in the world.

We will also perform the same task, but with the analysis of the lens.org platform (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Bibliometric analysis of the main authors by citation, who conducted research on green tourism in the work of international tour operators based on the lens.org platform (author research using the VOSviewer 1.19 program)

With regard to the results of this bibliometric analysis, close ties have been established between representatives of scientific schools in Asia, which investigate the processes of green tourism in the work of international tour operators.

It should be noted that the functionality of the lens.org platform [22] does not provide for author search by country of origin.

We will investigate the main prerequisites and factors for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies, based on the analyzed scientific works [1-19], which are devoted to green tourism.

The main prerequisites are: innovative prerequisites – in the promotion of the economic system of companies to technological structures of a higher level in order to increase the level of competitiveness of tourist services; economic prerequisites – when the added value is increased through the introduction of environmentally-oriented measures in the tourism sphere, as a trigger for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 6-8, 11-15); personnel prerequisites – in the formation of personnel support of tourist companies with green thinking as a component of the promotion of creative ideas in the field of green tourism, which affects the increase in the differentiation of tourist services of international tour operators; organizational prerequisites – in the formation of organizational systems of tourism companies that are focused on customer orientation in the field of green tourism and the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 6-8, 11-15).

Regarding the factors of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies (SDG 6-8, 11-15), the following should be included: the resource efficiency factor (SDG 6-8, 11) – in the formation of clean water, energy, the growth of jobs in the tourism sector and the formation of the sustainability of cities and communities, as a center of green culture in the implementation of green tourism; environmental protection factor (SDG 12, 14, 15) – with careful consumption and provision of tourist services, preservation of marine fauna and land resources in the implementation of green tourism; climate change factor (SDG 13) – when taking into account green tourism destinations by international tour operators.

We will form proposals for the development of green tourism in the context of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies at the level of the EU countries and Ukraine, taking into account its post-war state on the basis of the importance of using the results of bibliometric analysis for the formation of modern directions for the development of green tourism in the activities of international tour operators.

The main proposals include:

- according to the goal of SDG 6 (clean water and sanitation), in the implementation of green tourism by international tourism companies, there is a need to commission tourist services aimed at protecting the water environment, forming a careful attitude of tourists to water resources, creating information maps of water sources for free refilling of water, especially in cities and visiting water protected areas. Regarding Ukrainian tour operators, there is a need to develop the infrastructure of mobile water purification units at limited domestic tourism locations, to develop tourist services in Zakarpattia (lakes, mountain rivers);
- according to the goal of SDG 7 (affordable and clean energy), during the implementation of green tourism, international travel companies of EU countries must use tourist services that are aimed at visiting wind, solar and hydrothermal energy facilities and forming a careful attitude to energy consumption in customers. Regarding Ukrainian tour operators, there is a need to develop solar energy services (solar batteries, batteries, power banks for tourists);
- according to the goal of SDG 8 (decent work and economic growth), during the implementation of green tourism by international travel companies of the EU countries, it is necessary to form training courses for employees of travel companies and new jobs for tour operators that are oriented towards ecological tourism through national programs to support such initiatives. As for Ukrainian tour operators, the formation of new jobs for tour operators can take place primarily in the territories that are the rear areas (West of Ukraine) in the implementation of domestic tourism, the same applies to training programs for employees of travel companies;
- according to the goal of SDG 11 (sustainable cities and communities), during the implementation of green tourism by international tourism companies of the EU countries, it is necessary to form road maps of green tourist places in cities (park areas, water locations, green construction of buildings and structures as objects of tourist routes) . Regarding the implementation of the activities of Ukrainian tour operators, there is a need to strengthen the protection of cities and villages with air defense and missile defense systems by the armed forces of Ukraine against missile attacks;
- according to the goal of SDG 2 (responsible consumption and production), during the implementation of green tourism by international tourism companies of the EU countries, it is necessary to carry out tourist activities with a vector of caring attitude towards nature, to form directions of industrial tourism with visits to non-working factories (the experience of German tourist companies in Dresden, Berlin). Regarding the implementation of the activities of Ukrainian tour operators, there is a need for a careful attitude to water sources in order to form its stock and restore it in war conditions;
- according to the goal of SDG 13 (climate action), in the course of the implementation of green tourism by international tourism companies of the EU countries, it is necessary to form new tourist services that are

- oriented towards green tourism in the agricultural sector (visiting tree planting locations by logging companies, green agriculture). Regarding the implementation of the activities of Ukrainian tour operators, there is a need to preserve the forest landscapes of Zakarpattia and Prykarpattia from industrial deforestation, which, although it reduced its volume during the war, is implemented in these regions of Ukraine;
- according to the goal of SDG 14 (life below water), during the implementation of green tourism, international travel companies of EU countries must provide tourist services aimed at tourists visiting marine fauna and flora, marine archipelagos and protected areas through diving and snorkeling, visiting farms for growing sea snails as generators of sea water purification). Regarding the implementation of the activities of Ukrainian tour operators, there is a need to limit such services to the locations of mountain rivers and lakes of Zakarpattia in order to increase the safety of tourists in the implementation of green tourism;
 - according to the goal of SDG 15 (life on land), during the implementation of green tourism by international tourism companies of the EU countries, it is necessary to develop tourist services that are focused on increasing the potential of land resources, biodiversity through the attraction of tourists to the careful attitude of land resources, reducing the level of land pollution and applying ecological damage, attracting tourists to reforestation. Regarding the implementation of the activities of Ukrainian tour operators, there is a need to develop forest tourism in the natural reserves of Zakarpattia and Prykarpattia regions under the conditions of a low level of danger in these regions of Ukraine.

Conclusions

The main conclusions of the study include: an analysis of scientific works devoted to green tourism in the course of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies; a bibliometric analysis of green tourism was carried out and the dependence of various definitions on the concept of green tourism, activities of various representatives of scientific schools of the world countries in the direction of the development of the theory of green tourism development were established; the main prerequisites (innovative, economic, personnel, organizational) and factors of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies were investigated, which include the following factors: resource efficiency, environmental protection, and climate change. Also, the authors suggested for each Sustainable Development Goal to outline the directions of green tourism at the level of the EU countries and Ukraine, taking into account its post-war state. Further scientific research should be aimed at the bibliometric analysis of the main modern topics of green tourism for the purpose of submitting grant applications in grant projects of the European Union, such as the Erasmus program, Horizon 2020 and for the purpose of forming effective organizational and economic support for green tourism in these projects.

Abstract

Introduction. In terms of the accelerated development of productive forces, the movement to Industry 5.0 and the transition of business processes to their sustainable development, international tourism companies pay more and more attention to their sustainability and the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals, which actualizes the topic of the research. The direction of green tourism corresponds to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 6-8, 11-15) and is one of the directions of effective work of international tourism companies in the world market of tourist services.

The main goal of this study is to conduct a bibliometric analysis of green tourism in the context of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies. The main tasks of the research include the following elements: to analyze the main representatives of scientific currents of green tourism in the work of international companies, to conduct a bibliometric analysis of green tourism of international tourism companies by directions (keywords, main representatives, geographical distribution of scientific schools) on various bibliometric platforms, to form the main prerequisites and factors for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by tour operators, to formulate proposals for the development of green tourism in the context of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies at the level of EU countries and Ukraine, taking into account its post-war state. Research results. In the course of the conducted bibliometric analysis, the main scientific schools and scientists in the world who study green tourism were considered. When conducting a bibliometric analysis, the interaction of the main definitions that interact with the definition of green tourism was revealed.

The main prerequisites and factors for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies have been studied. Proposals for the development of green tourism in the context of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by international tourism companies at the level of EU countries and Ukraine have been formulated, taking into account its post-war state. Research conclusion. The main conclusion is the substantiation of the bibliometric analysis of green tourism of international tourism companies. Further scientific research should be aimed at the bibliometric analysis of the main modern topics of green tourism for the purpose of submitting grant applications in grant projects of the European Union, such as the Erasmus program, Horizon 2020 and for the purpose of forming effective organizational and economic support for green tourism in these projects.

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